

ISic2751

I.Sicily inscription 2751

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico

Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331799

1. Στουδιῶ-

2. σε #⁵⁶ χρηστὲ

3. χαίρε #⁵⁶ ἔζη-

4. σε #⁵⁶ ἔτη #⁵⁶ ξ □

5. λυδιαστής.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645154

EDCS 65300226

PHI 331799

Bibliography

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